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LEARNING TO LEARN: AN EVALUATION OF THE LEARNING THEORIES OF STANISLAS DEHAENE AND THEIR SUITABILITY FOR ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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1. INTRODUCTION

As most competent engineers know all too-well, successful operation of complex machinery requires deep familiarity with the manual and specifications of the machine. Unfortunately, when it comes to education, a good manual for the machine, the student, is not available. This can lead to engineering educators absolving themselves from responsibility to learn how their students learn, and to rely on tried and tested methods, which is often the ‘chalk and talk’ approach that they experienced in their own engineering formation, perhaps updated from chalk to smartboard. In a paper for REES 2015 [1], a survey of engineering faculty in DIT revealed the following:

Twenty-five staff responded. The median number of years in engineering education was 15, with a low of 4 and a high of 30 years.

Table 1: Survey of Engineering Faculty and education interest

	Years Teaching Engineering	Education Qualification	Interest in the discipline of engineering education	Read any paper in an engineering education journal in the past year? E.g. JEE, IJEE	Read any paper in an engineering education journal in the past 5 years? E.g. JEE, IJEE	Attended an engineering education conference? E.g. SEFI
Mean	14.32	36%	64%	68%	72%	32%

It is good that a majority expressed an interest in engineering education, but disappointing that less than a third had ever attended an engineering education conference such as SEFI.

It is a pity that so many are not involved in the domain of engineering education, not least because the last twenty years has seen an enormous growth in our understanding of how the human brain learns. We are closer than ever to having that

'learning manual'. Not to use this knowledge as part of our own educational toolkit, is a wasted opportunity for both students and educators.

This paper examines closely the work of one such researcher into how the brain learns, the French cognitive neuroscientist, Stanislaus Dehaene. Dehaene is a professor at the Collège de France and, since 1989, the director of INSERM Unit 562, "Cognitive Neuroimaging". Although he originally trained as a mathematician, he changed course after reading Pierre Changeux's book, *L'Homme neuronal*. He collaborated with Changeux on computational neuronal models of human cognition. He received a doctorate in experimental psychology at the École des Hautes Études en Sciences Sociales (EHESS), Paris in 1989. Dehaene is perhaps best known for his work on numerical cognition, *La Bosse des Maths (The Number Sense)* in 1997. His biography from the Collège de France states:

Stanislas Dehaene's interests concern the cerebral bases of specifically human cognitive functions such as language, calculation, and reasoning. The team uses a variety of experimental methods, including mental chronometry in normal subjects, cognitive analyses of brain-lesioned patients, and brain-imaging studies with positron emission tomography, functional magnetic resonance imaging, and high-density recordings of event-related potentials. Formal models of minimal neuronal networks are also devised and simulated in an attempt to throw some links between molecular, physiological, imaging, and behavioral data. [2]

In 2020, Dehaene published *How We Learn* [3], an overview of current neurological models of learning. His analysis is particularly relevant for STEM educators as he states that the human child learns like a scientist, creating mental models of the outside world and continuously validating them.

This paper consists of two main sections, the first an overview of Dehaene's theory of learning, as described in *How We Learn*, and the second section an examination of the ways in which this theory could be applied to engineering education.

2.0 HOW WE LEARN

Dehaene begins in his Introduction by reflecting on why animals learn. In the case of a human being, the information encoded in our genes is, at 750 megabytes, simply too small to encompass not just the instructions for building and maintaining a human body, but also all the information that body would need to survive. But even for an extremely simple creature, such as a nematode worm, where it could be encoded in the genes, he argues that natural selection prefers learning:

With such a small number of neurons, the worm's behavior could have been fully pre-wired. However, it is not. The reason is that it is highly advantageous, indeed indispensable for its survival, to adapt to the specific environment in which it is born. Even two genetically identical organisms will not necessarily encounter the same ecosystem. In the case of the nematode, the ability to quickly adjust its behavior to the density, chemistry, and temperature of the place in which it lands allows it to be more efficient. [4]

Dehaene goes on to redefine *homo sapiens* as *homo docens*, the learning animal. It is this quality that elevates humans to the apex of the animal kingdom:

If I had to sum up, in one word, the singular talents of our species, I would answer with "learning." We are not simply Homo sapiens, but Homo docens—the species

that teaches itself. Most of what we know about the world was not given to us by our genes: we had to learn it from our environment or from those around us. No other animal has managed to change its ecological niche so radically, moving from the African savanna to deserts, mountains, islands, polar ice caps, cave dwellings, cities, and even outer space, all within a few thousand years. Learning has fueled it all. From making fire and designing stone tools to agriculture, exploration, and atomic fission, the story of humanity is one of constant self-reinvention. At the root of all these accomplishments lies one secret: the extraordinary ability of our brain to formulate hypotheses and select those that fit with our environment...

In our species, the contribution of learning is particularly large since our childhood extends over many more years than it does for other mammals. And because we possess a unique knack for language and mathematics, our learning device is able to navigate vast spaces of hypotheses that recombine into potentially infinite sets—even if they are always grounded in fixed and invariable foundations inherited from our evolution.

The tragedy for Dehaene is that so much is now known about the learning algorithms that the human brain has devolved over millions of years of evolution, but most educators are not consciously aware of these, and proceed to teach intuitively, a methodology that is at best hit and miss. We have the knowledge:

Thirty years of research, at the boundaries of computer science, neurobiology, and cognitive psychology, have largely elucidated the algorithms that our brain uses, the circuits involved, the factors that modulate their efficacy, and the reasons why they are uniquely efficient in humans. [4]

One example he gives is the excellent website provided by the British Educational Endowment Foundation (EEF). The EEF website lists and describes many different teaching strategies and their proven efficacy. [5] What distinguishes this site from many others is that it is evidence based, relying on a meta-analysis of many educational research papers. The strategy that scores highest on this website is quite simple: feedback, which it summarises as 'high impact for low-cost', based on moderate evidence.

This website is key to understanding Dehaene's mission: educators need to know how students learn, and apply proven strategies that further that aim. Experience and intuition are just not enough.

Dehaene identifies four pillars of learning:

focused attention, active engagement, error feedback, and a cycle of daily rehearsal and nightly consolidation [4]

The first pillar, attention, is an essential survival strategy. Animals that are prey, pay very close attention to sights and sounds around them, as failure to hear the big cat making his approach can, and will, prove fatal. Humans are long removed from the plains of Africa, where a naked ape with very few natural defences had to pay attention or die. As most educators know all too well, attention is a very scarce commodity in the classroom. We are the first generation of educators who have to compete with smartphones for our students' attention! But if our students are not paying attention during a lecture, they will learn very little. Or as Dehaene puts it in terms of the brains functioning:

With conscious attention, the discharges of the sensory and conceptual neurons that code for an object are massively amplified and prolonged, and their messages propagate into the prefrontal cortex, where whole populations of neurons ignite and fire for a long time, well beyond the original duration of the image. Such a strong surge of neural firing is exactly what synapses need in order to change their strength—what neuroscientists call “long-term potentiation.” When a pupil pays conscious attention to, say, a foreign-language word that the teacher has just introduced, she allows that word to deeply propagate into her cortical circuits, all the way into the prefrontal cortex. As a result, that word has a much better chance of being remembered. Unconscious or unattended words remain largely confined to the brain’s sensory circuits, never getting a chance to reach the deeper lexical and conceptual representations that support comprehension and semantic memory. [6]

However, Dehaene doesn’t give up the battle for students’ attention easily. Recognizing that video games grab attention very well, his lab has developed a number of video games to teach mathematics!

Dehaene’s second pillar is active engagement. As he puts it succinctly, passive organisms do not learn:

To learn, our brain must first form a hypothetical mental model of the outside world, which it then projects onto its environment and puts to a test by comparing its predictions to what it receives from the senses. This algorithm implies an active, engaged, and attentive posture. Motivation is essential: we learn well only if we have a clear goal and we fully commit to reaching it. [7]

This attention affects the memory. Depth processing of word lists leads to better recall, e.g. if one group of subjects are asked which of 60 words are uppercase, and the other group, which of them are animal names, the subjects who had to think about animals recalled more of the 60 words.

The third pillar is error correction. This chapter begins by quoting Theodore Roosevelt, “The only man who never makes a mistake is the man who never does anything” [8] He makes a clear statement about the centrality of feedback: “it would be practically impossible to progress if we did not start off by failing. Errors always recede as long as we receive feedback that tells us how to improve. This is why error feedback is the third pillar of learning, and one of the most influential educational parameters: the quality and accuracy of the feedback we receive determines how quickly we learn.” [8]

That feedback need not be external. Recall that the brain functions as a scientific modeller: if the expected input does not arrive, the brain adjusts its internal model. A key part of this adjustment comes from the feeling of surprise: the person expected x, but is surprised to get y!

The fourth pillar is consolidation: “which happens in all domains: a shift from slow, conscious, and effortful processing to fast, unconscious, and automatic expertise. Our brains never stop learning. Even when a skill is mastered, we continue to overlearn it.” [9]

But how does the human brain consolidate? Dehaene’s reveals the importance of sleep in learning, an aspect of sleep only discovered in the last three decades:

...learning is much more efficient when done at regular intervals: rather than cramming an entire lesson into one day, we are better off spreading out the learning.

The reason is simple: every night, our brain consolidates what it has learned during the day. This is one of the most important neuroscience discoveries of the last thirty years: sleep is not just a period of inactivity or a garbage collection of the waste products that the brain accumulated while we were awake. Quite the contrary: while we sleep, our brain remains active; it runs a specific algorithm that replays the important events it recorded during the previous day and gradually transfers them into a more efficient compartment of our memory. [10]

This is a very important discovery, but unfortunately it presents great challenges to university educators: how to persuade students to get a good night's sleep!

3.0 HOW CAN WE LEARN FROM HOW WE LEARN?

Julius Caesar begins his account of his nine year campaign against the Gauls with the geographic phrase, Gallia est omnis divisa in partes tres [11], Gaul as a whole is divided into three parts.

There are many challenges for engineering educators in Dehaene's work. Each of the pillars provides a way to improve students' learning, but none of them are easy.

The first pillar, attention, is difficult in an era of smart phones. It is also very difficult to measure, as a student looking at a lecturer, or a screen, could easily be daydreaming.

In the Handbook of Attention [12], Olney et al, have a chapter, Attention in Educational Contexts: The Role of the Learning Task in Guiding Attention, in which they suggest that the learning attention is determined by the task, which they rate as follows:

“the Interactive–Constructive–Active–Passive (ICAP) hypothesis predicts that task type (as defined by overt behaviours) will largely determine learning outcomes and rank orders the effectiveness of these activities as $I \geq C \geq A \geq P$ ”

In this model, P, passive, is defined as simply listening to a lecture, live or recorded. A, active, is note taking, c, constructive, is having to summarise, or explain the notes taken down.

I, or interactive, is when there is dialogue between student and educator. For obvious reasons, this is a small component of most lectures in large groups, due to the time constraints.

The best strategy within normal resources, is to get students to C-type activities, perhaps by using Tony Buzan's Mind Maps [13]. This is a technique of visually representing the links in a document or lecture. Students could be assessed on the quality of their Mind Maps, covering different topics, such as Heat transfer.

Figure 1: Mind Map of the late Tony Buzan's career [14]

Another way of looking at the attention-learning issue, is in the context of Benjamin Bloom's Taxonomy, where the aim is to get the students to move to higher cognitive activity, which in itself forces the brain to pay attention.

Figure 2: Bloom's Cognitive taxonomy [15]

Creating Mind Maps, at the very least, moves the learning activity up to Analysis and Synthesis.

Another approach is to meet students in their milieu. Dehaene's labs write games that aid the learning of mathematics. Is it possible for engineering educators to write apps that will grab and hold students' attention, whilst teaching core concepts? This would require a lot of resources, and cross institution collaboration, but could prove very worthwhile.

Active engagement is an area that has been tackled in educational research for a number of years. One such method is the flipped classroom, where students have to take the active role of the teacher. Australian educators Anne Gardner and Keith Willey have written extensively on this topic, and have presented papers at REES and SEFI on the topic. [16]

Another approach to active learning is open ended problems, an area developed by, amongst other, Louis Bucciarelli of MIT. Following on from Professor Bucciarelli's visit to TU Dublin in 2009, a number of projects have been undertaken in this area and reported at SEFI 2013 [17] and CISPEE 2018 [18]

Consolidation is a difficult issue, as it involves students getting regular sleep. But it also imposes constraints on academics as well. Students need to take in bite-sized pieces of information and digest it, over 8-hours of slumber. This strongly suggests that lectures should also be bite-sized, and those such as an unnamed Head of

Department who thought a 3-hour calculus lecture on a Monday afternoon was a really neat idea, should think again. Timetables must reflect human attention span, and also, consolidation span.

Dehaene's third pillar is perhaps the most interesting for engineering educators. His insight is that the human brain makes models of the world, that it successively refines by error-correction. This is, of course, the way in which science and engineering proceed. Why not make that relationship explicit? A first-year module on how both babies and scientists create and refine models, should help students grasp the modus operandi of science and engineering, and give them a life-long appreciation of models and their limitations.

There are so many ways to do this. Teaching by examples is one: The failure of the Tacoma narrows bridge in 1940, could be presented not as a failure of the design model, but of the limitations of the model, which did not include aero-elastic flutter. Subsequent models did, because engineering, like science, learns only from failure.

Models and their limitations are also behind our daily decision making. April 2020 is the 50th anniversary of the Apollo 13 accident, which nearly led to the loss of the crew. Although NASA likes to focus on the successful rescue, it rarely mentions the poor decision making that led to the accident. Chief among them was the launch engineer's ignoring of a problem with the liquid oxygen tank on fuel cell 2 in the service module. His model of the fuel cell was incomplete, being unaware that the heating circuit was designed to run on 28 V, but was running on 65 V. Using the heater to empty the faulty tank in pre-launch tests burnt the cables, leading to a spark two days after launch.

This leads to one of Dehaene's central ideas: meta-cognition leads to better learning, and better results. Too much of human activity is done on auto-pilot. Reflection, or meta-cognition, is a vital skill for all, but especially engineers. It can, and should, be explicitly taught.

A final lesson for engineering education: Mindset. Dehaene discusses the work of Carol Dweck, the Stanford Psychologist, who has spent over 25 years examining why some students learn and others don't. Dweck identifies two mindsets, fixed and growth. Fixed minds make little effort, relying on their ability. If their ability is not enough, they quit, usually blaming someone or something for their failure.

Growth mindset people know they have to work. They accept failure along the way as a challenge, a lesson, not a reason to give up. [19]

The application of Mindset to engineering education has been examined by the TU Dublin team, for example at SEFI 2019. [20] As Carol Dweck's work shows, and as the 2019 SEFI paper shows with regard to engineering, this is a skill that can be taught, and does lead to an improvement in students' learning.

4.0 CONCLUSION

In the aftermath of the Fukushima disaster, careful monitoring of the radiation levels at the site was essential for the health and safety of the Tepco workers trying to deal with six damaged nuclear reactors. Fortunately, recorded levels were consistently around the 100 mSv/hr level, high, but not too high. Unfortunately, they were too consistent. Always and everywhere around the plant, levels were 100 mSv/hr. When, after some months the monitoring team actually read the manuals, they discovered

that the instruments that they were using had a maximum reading of... 100 mSv/hr. They were designed for normal plant operation, not reactors with exposed cores.

The failure of engineering educators to read the manual, in other words to better understand how students learn, is not as serious as miss-reading radiation levels, both from a professional and an ethical point of view. However, the world needs more engineers, and if we can facilitate this by aligning our teaching methods with the brain's learning algorithms, then we will be doing a better job, for ourselves, our students, and the world.

It would be good if an organisation such as SEFI would undertake to produce a website, similar to the EEF's, with information on specific learning strategies for engineering education, backed by solid research evidence.

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